

General superspace non-Abelian gauge transformations isomorphic to groups of spacetime tetrad Lorentz transformations in four-dimensional Lorentzian flat spacetimes

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The extended superspace generalized local gauge transformations are studied under a new light. We have previously proved that the local internal gauge symmetry groups of the Standard Model are isomorphic to local tensor products of the local one-dimensional group LB1. Independently to LB2 as well. LB1 is $SO(1,1)$ plus two different kinds of discrete transformations, one of them non-Lorentzian. LB2 is $SO(2)$. All of this in curved four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes. LB1 was proved to be isomorphic to LB2. That is, a non-compact group plus two discrete transformations, isomorphic to a compact group. Special tetrads were defined such that they are locally gauge dependent. In such a way that when a local gauge transformation is carried out, these tetrads transform on one hand in a local plane one determined by the timelike and one spacelike tetrad vectors under LB1. Independently, on the other hand, these tetrads transform on the local plane two determined by the other two spacelike tetrad vectors, under LB2. The local planes one and two are orthogonal. The local tetrad vectors do not leave their original local planes under local gauge transformations and this is crucial for the metric tensor to remain invariant. On a local plane one or two spanned by just two of our tetrad vectors with a single and unique structure like a unique extremal field-gauge vector structure, the tensor product of one-dimensional groups like LB1 on the local plane one or LB2 on local plane two, would just be one-dimensional. However this is not the case we are discussing in this manuscript and we will clarify this situation during the analysis. In this note we will implement the construction of new tetrads and find additional isomorphisms between superspace generalized local supergauge non-Abelian transformations and spacetime local tetrad transformations, following a similar line of reasoning even though the spacetime will be considered flat in our proofs. The applicability of such a notion would be raised immediately. We therefore conjecture about the possibility of superspace to become relevant during the annihilation dynamical evolution. Because a certain number of variables are necessary in order to build the tetrads that might undergo a local transformation from non-null into null. We conjecture the possibility that during an annihilation process of two leptons, an electron and a positron for instance, the pure four-dimensional spacetime in which these leptons exist is extended both in coordinates and fields such that superspace becomes relevant. We will follow a similar course to previous work in this paper, in

order to prove analogous theorems between local groups of superspace non-Abelian supergauge transformations and local groups of tetrad transformations.

I. INTRODUCTION

We conjecture the possibility that during an annihilation process of two leptons, an electron and a positron for instance, the pure four-dimensional spacetime in which these leptons exist is extended both in coordinates and fields such that generalized non-Abelian gauge transformations become relevant. We have already proved in previous works that all the local internal gauge groups of transformations associated to the Standard Model are isomorphic to local groups of spacetime tetrad transformations. Since all the local gauge symmetries can be realized in four-dimensional Lorentz spacetimes, then it is valid to wonder if it is possible to associate four-dimensional spacetimes to microparticles like electrons or positrons. The fact that several local groups of gauge transformations have been proved isomorphic to local groups of tetrad transformations in four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes encourages us to think about the possibility of similar results for superspace local supergauge groups of transformations. The new tetrads introduced in manuscripts^{1,2,3} function as a bridge between both group structures. Two construction elements are fundamental in these new tetrad structures, the skeletons and the gauge vectors. It is precisely these skeletons and gauge vectors the tools that have been used in order to prove the theorems about isomorphisms between local gauge groups like $U(1)$ and $SU(2) \times U(1)$, and the local spacetime groups of tetrad transformations in four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes^{1,2,3}. We will follow a similar procedure in this paper in order to prove analogous theorems between groups of superspace non-Abelian local supergauge transformations and local groups of tetrad transformations. At every point in spacetime these new tetrads define two orthogonal planes or blades that are spanned, one of them, plane one, by the timelike and one spacelike vector, and the other, plane two, by the remaining two spacelike vectors. These tetrad vectors have two structural components in their construction. First the skeleton, which is a local gauge invariant. Second, the gauge vector. Gauge vectors are gauge per se, and they include gauge in their construction. Under local gauge transformations, the two vectors that span plane one, do not leave plane one and transform under the local LB1, and similar for plane two under the local LB2. This means that the metric tensor is a manifest local invariant under local gauge transformations. This property is a fundamental foundational stone on which the theorems that prove the isomorphisms between the local gauge groups of the Standard Model and local groups of tetrad transformations are

demonstrated. In the Abelian case it was proved that the local group of electromagnetic gauge transformations $U(1)$ is isomorphic to both the local groups LB1 and LB2, separately, independently. Therefore proving by transitivity that the group LB1 is isomorphic to LB2. That is, in paper¹ it was proved that the non-compact group of boosts $SO(1, 1)$ plus two discrete transformations is isomorphic to the compact group $SO(2)$. Rendering the hypotheses made at the outset of the no-go theorems from the sixties, empty. The no-go theorems^{4,5,6} rely on two fundamental hypotheses made a priori of these theorems. The internal transformations take place in an abstract space. It has been assumed that the generators of the internal and spacetime groups commute. We proved that the locally “internal” groups $SU(2)$ and $U(1)$ are isomorphic to local “spacetime” groups of tetrad transformations on special local planes, and therefore the assumption is not true simply because local Lorentz transformations do not commute in general. It has also been assumed that there are no finite-dimensional unitary representations of non-compact groups. Since LB1 groups (local boosts plus discrete transformations) are isomorphic to LB2 groups (local spatial rotations), then this is not true either, see references^{1,3}. It has been thought for a long time⁴⁻⁷ that the spacetime and internal groups of local transformations are detached from each other. This has been proved manifestly incorrect. The next step was then to see if a similar geometrical landscape was true for superspace generalized supergauge⁸⁻¹¹ transformations of tetrads in four-dimensional Lorentzian flat spacetimes. That is, we set out to build local tetrad skeletons that are locally invariant under the superspace generalized gauge group of transformations. It is the goal of this paper to study if it is possible to build tetrad gauge vectors that allow to prove similar isomorphisms to the ones already proved for $U(1)$ in paper¹ or $SU(2) \times U(1)$ in manuscript³. Exclusively regarding the isomorphisms we intend to prove, we are not talking about an extended coordinate structure including Grassmann variables, in the same sense as in standard theories of strings¹², where there is a process of compactification. We are considering the possibility that these extended coordinate structures might play a partial role in the annihilation process, more in the sense of “internal” transformations isomorphic to LB1 and LB2, having as the example-pattern, that of paper³, in the sense of invariant skeleton structures. Standard quantum field theories consider electrons and positrons as point structures. We wonder if they are not point particles, such that these extended coordinate and field superspace structures manifest mathematically in the dynamical evolution of tetrad skeletons and gauge vectors. That is the other sense of

our conjecture or assumption. We can interpret an evolution from an initial state with non-null tetrads associated to the geometry of electrons and positrons in pure four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes and successively the tetrad skeletons and gauge vectors evolve in an extended coordinate and field structure of a superspace nature during the annihilation, into a final state of null tetrads associated to bosonic fields, once again in pure four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes. Finally, setting aside all these conjectures and possible applications of these superspace extended coordinate and field structures, we must emphasize that all the results in sections II and III have mathematical validity by themselves. Independently of any of our previous assumptions and conjectures about possible applications, the following mathematical results are true by themselves. We conjecture that the spacetimes associated to microparticles will be curved. However, we can prove these isomorphism theorems between local supergauge groups in superspace on one hand and local groups of tetrads transformations on the other, in flat Minkowskian spacetime.

II. NEW TETRAD GENERALIZED GAUGE INVARIANT SKELETONS

We will let the two-spinor θ^a transform as the fundamental representation of $SL(2, C)$ where $a = 1, 2$. The complex conjugate two-spinors will be labeled as $\bar{\theta}^{\dot{a}}$ where $\dot{a} = \dot{1}, \dot{2}$ and they transform under the complex conjugate representation of $SL(2, C)$, an inequivalent representation to the fundamental representation of $SL(2, C)$, see reference⁷. From the literature⁷⁻¹¹ and sections V-VI it is established that we can define the following derivative operators,

$$D_a = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^a} - \iota (\sigma^\mu \bar{\theta})_a \partial_\mu \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{D}_{\dot{a}} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{\theta}^{\dot{a}}} + \iota (\theta \sigma^\mu)_{\dot{a}} \partial_\mu . \quad (2)$$

In the Abelian case if V is a vector superfield, we can also define⁷⁻⁹ chiral superfields $W_a = \frac{\iota}{4} \bar{D}^2 D_a V$ such that they satisfy,

$$\bar{D}_{\dot{a}} W_a = 0 . \quad (3)$$

We can also define the conjugate chiral superfields $\bar{W}_{\dot{a}}$ such that they fulfill,

$$D_a \bar{W}_{\dot{a}} = 0 . \quad (4)$$

The object $W_a = \frac{i}{4} \bar{D}^2 D_a V$ is invariant under the local superspace generalized Abelian transformation $V \rightarrow V - \frac{i}{2} (\Lambda - \Lambda^\dagger)$. These results can be verified in the literature, for instance in reference⁹.

In the non-Abelian case the gauge degrees of freedom take values in the associated Lie algebra spanned by the Hermitian generators T^k ,

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_k T^k \quad V = V_k T^k \quad [T^h, T^k] = i f^{hkm} T_m .$$

In the non-Abelian case we can define⁹ the generalized chiral field,

$$W_a = -\frac{1}{8g} (\bar{D}_{\dot{a}} \bar{D}^{\dot{a}}) \exp(-2qV) D_a \exp(2qV) . \quad (5)$$

We would like to define an object, see reference⁹, that is invariant under local non-Abelian generalized gauge transformations. The vector superfield exponential under non-Abelian generalized local gauge transformations becomes,

$$\exp(2qV) \rightarrow \exp(i q \Lambda^\dagger) \exp(2qV) \exp(-i q \Lambda) . \quad (6)$$

Let us recall that in this non-Abelian case we have the vector superfield generalized gauge transformations $V \rightarrow V - \frac{i}{2} (\Lambda - \Lambda^\dagger) - \frac{iq}{2} [V, \Lambda + \Lambda^\dagger] + \dots$. The chiral field (5) transforms as,

$$W_a \rightarrow \exp(i q \Lambda) W_a \exp(-i q \Lambda) . \quad (7)$$

Matter chiral fields transform as,

$$\phi \rightarrow \exp(i q \Lambda) \phi \quad (8)$$

Then, the new generalized non-Abelian local gauge invariant object can be defined as,

$$Z_a = \phi^\dagger \exp(2qV) W_a \phi . \quad (9)$$

A similar object $\bar{Z}_{\dot{a}}$ can be defined for $\bar{W}_{\dot{a}}$. With all these elements that can be checked in standard literature like references⁷⁻⁹ for instance, we can proceed to define two auxiliary second rank antisymmetric fields in this flat Minkowskian background.

$$\varepsilon^{\mu\nu} = Z^a (\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a{}^b Z_b \quad (10)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^{\mu\nu} = \bar{Z}_{\dot{a}} (\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{a}}{}_{\dot{b}} \bar{Z}^{\dot{b}} . \quad (11)$$

These two second rank antisymmetric objects in spacetime, see a discussion of the objects $(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a{}^b$ and $(\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{a}}{}_{\dot{b}}$ in section V, are both local superspace generalized non-Abelian gauge invariants. It can be verified⁷⁻⁹ that $(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a{}^b \dagger = (\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{b}}{}_{\dot{a}}$ and $(\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{a}}{}_{\dot{b}} \dagger = (\sigma^{\mu\nu})_b{}^a$. Then, we can introduce the real objects,

$$\epsilon_R^{\mu\nu} = (\varepsilon^{\mu\nu} + \bar{\varepsilon}^{\mu\nu})/2 \quad (12)$$

$$\epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} = (\varepsilon^{\mu\nu} - \bar{\varepsilon}^{\mu\nu})/(2i) . \quad (13)$$

These two objects (12-13) possess the right transformation properties under Lorentz transformations, see references^{13,14} and section V. These two objects can be combined as an extremal field tensor through the use of a local spacetime scalar field complexion α as,

$$e^{\mu\nu} = \cos \alpha \epsilon_R^{\mu\nu} - \sin \alpha \epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} . \quad (14)$$

The local scalar complexion α is defined by imposing the equation $\epsilon_{\mu\nu} * \epsilon^{\mu\nu} = 0$. We can also define the dual second rank antisymmetric tensor as $*\epsilon_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\sigma\tau} \epsilon^{\sigma\tau}$. Using the properties of the objects σ^α and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha$ from references⁷⁻¹⁵ and section V, we can prove that $\tan(2\alpha) = -\epsilon_{R\mu\nu} \epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} / \epsilon_{R\rho\lambda} \epsilon_R^{\rho\lambda}$. Using identities (29-30) from the first appendix, section V, it is straightforward to prove that $*\epsilon_R^{\mu\nu} = -\epsilon_I^{\mu\nu}$ and $*\epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} = \epsilon_R^{\mu\nu}$. This local angle α , known as the complexion¹⁶ can be found in terms of chiral superfields through equations (10-11) and the use of identities (31-33). Like antisymmetric fields in a four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetime, the extremal fields also verify the identity,

$$\epsilon_{\mu\alpha} \epsilon^{\nu\alpha} - *\epsilon_{\mu\alpha} * \epsilon^{\nu\alpha} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_\mu{}^\nu Q , \quad (15)$$

where $Q = \epsilon_{\mu\nu} \epsilon^{\mu\nu}$ and Q is assumed not to be zero. Condition $\epsilon_{\mu\nu} * \epsilon^{\mu\nu} = 0$ can be proved equivalent to another condition. Through the use of the general identity,

$$A_{\mu\alpha} B^{\nu\alpha} - *B_{\mu\alpha} *A^{\nu\alpha} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} A_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta} , \quad (16)$$

which is valid for every pair of antisymmetric tensors in a four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetime¹⁶, when applied to the case $A_{\mu\alpha} = \epsilon_{\mu\alpha}$ and $B^{\nu\alpha} = *\epsilon^{\nu\alpha}$ yields the equivalent condition,

$$\epsilon_{\rho\mu} * \epsilon^{\mu\nu} = 0 . \quad (17)$$

It is evident that identity (15) is a special case of (16). Next, reproducing exactly the procedure laid out in manuscripts^{1,2} we can present the following tetrad at every point in spacetime,

$$V_{(1)}^{\alpha} = \epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} \epsilon_{\rho\lambda} X^{\rho} \quad (18)$$

$$V_{(2)}^{\alpha} = \sqrt{-Q/2} \epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} X_{\lambda} \quad (19)$$

$$V_{(3)}^{\alpha} = \sqrt{-Q/2} * \epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} Y_{\lambda} \quad (20)$$

$$V_{(4)}^{\alpha} = *\epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} * \epsilon_{\rho\lambda} Y^{\rho} , \quad (21)$$

We would like to highlight several properties of vectors (18-21) already proven in papers^{1,2}. Two building structures are present in vectors (18-21). We can start with the skeleton. For vector (18) the skeleton is $\epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} \epsilon_{\rho\lambda}$, for vector (20) it would be $*\epsilon^{\alpha\lambda}$. Then, the gauge vectors. For (18-19) the gauge vector is X^{ρ} , for vectors (20-21) the gauge vector is Y^{ρ} . Through the use of equations (15-17) it is straightforward to prove that they are orthogonal. The gauge vectors will become, once defined, the tool that we will use in order to prove the theorems in section III. At every point in spacetime the two vectors (18-19) define a plane or blade one^{16,17}. The two vectors (20-21) a plane or blade two, orthogonal to plane one. We recall from the results in paper³ that the local non-Abelian gauge superspace invariance of the tetrad skeletons is crucial because it prevents the vectors in plane one from leaving the plane once we introduce superspace generalized local gauge transformations in the gauge vector X^{ρ} , and analogous for the gauge vector Y^{ρ} in plane two. This property secures the invariance of the metric tensor for the normalized version of vectors (18-21). We will discuss this issue thoroughly in section III.

III. THEOREMS

For the following analysis it is necessary to introduce the normalized version of tetrad (18-21),

$$U^\alpha = \epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} \epsilon_{\rho\lambda} X^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{X_\mu \epsilon^{\mu\sigma} \epsilon_{\nu\sigma} X^\nu}) \quad (22)$$

$$V^\alpha = \epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} X_\lambda / (\sqrt{X_\mu \epsilon^{\mu\sigma} \epsilon_{\nu\sigma} X^\nu}) \quad (23)$$

$$Z^\alpha = * \epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} Y_\lambda / (\sqrt{Y_\mu * \epsilon^{\mu\sigma} * \epsilon_{\nu\sigma} Y^\nu}) \quad (24)$$

$$W^\alpha = * \epsilon^{\alpha\lambda} * \epsilon_{\rho\lambda} Y^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{Y_\mu * \epsilon^{\mu\sigma} * \epsilon_{\nu\sigma} Y^\nu}) . \quad (25)$$

where $Q = \epsilon_{\mu\nu} \epsilon^{\mu\nu}$ was already assumed not to be zero in section II. The normalization factors are assumed not to produce divergences. The next step would be to make a choice for the gauge vectors. A possible and useful choice is $X^\sigma = Y^\sigma = Tr[\Sigma^{\alpha\beta} E_\alpha^\rho E_\beta^\lambda * \xi_\rho^\sigma * \xi_{\lambda\tau} V^\tau]$. The gauge potential V_μ^k is related to the super field strength through,

$$F_{\mu\nu}^k = \partial_\mu V_\nu^k - \partial_\nu V_\mu^k + q f_{de}^k V_\mu^d V_\nu^e . \quad (26)$$

where k is the internal index, in the $SU(2)$ case $k : 1 \dots 3$. These definitions are taken from reference⁹. The object $\Sigma^{\alpha\beta}$ is discussed in section V. The tensor $\xi_{\mu\nu}$ is the Abelian extremal field, introduced in a previous manuscript¹⁸ dealing with Abelian gauge transformations in superspace. The structure $E_{[\alpha}^\rho E_{\beta]}^\lambda * \xi_\rho^\sigma * \xi_{\lambda\tau}$ is an Abelian local gauge super invariant. The proof of this invariance is equivalent to the proof in four-dimensional spacetimes provided in manuscript³. The tetrads E_β^λ are the $U(1)$ Abelian normalized tetrads introduced in the same previous work where the Abelian gauge transformations in superspace were studied, see paper¹⁸. The infinitesimal version of the local gauge transformations of the non-Abelian potential V_μ^k is, $V_\mu^k \rightarrow V_\mu^k - \partial_\mu \epsilon^k - g \epsilon^{kmn} \epsilon^m V_\mu^n$, with k, m and n internal indices and ϵ^k the three infinitesimal transformation local parameters. Once we introduce the local gauge transformations of the non-Abelian potential V_μ^k , the proof for the isomorphism theorems stated next, would follow the exact lines of reasoning as the ones for the local gauge transformations in standard non-Abelian gauge theories such as the one presented in manuscript³.

Since the steps are a mathematical replica of our isomorphism theorems already proved

for the pure non-Abelian field in manuscript³, we state these results in the following two theorems,

Theorem 1 *The mapping between the group of non-Abelian local supergauge transformations in superspace and the group of $(\otimes LB1)^3$ local tetrad transformations is isomorphic.*

By similar reasoning to the one laid out in³, in addition to all the ideas above, we can also state,

Theorem 2 *The mapping between the group of non-Abelian local supergauge transformations in superspace and the group of $(\otimes LB2)^3$ local tetrad transformations is isomorphic.*

It is very important that we make a clarification on an issue that might give rise to confusion. It is clear that if we have a local plane one or two spanned by tetrad vectors with just a single and only extremal field-gauge vector structure and we consider only on this plane one-dimensional groups of transformations, such as LB1 for the local plane one or LB2 for the local plane two, which is nothing but $SO(2)$, and furthermore, we consider tensor products of these tetrad local groups of transformations on this particular local plane, we can conclude that these tensor products are reduced to simple LB1 or LB2 local groups of transformations. This is not what we mean in the enunciation of isomorphism theorems between $SU(2)$ supergauge and $(\otimes LB1)^3$, for instance. In these theorems we are considering three copies of the same spacetime, and a different tetrad at the same point in each spacetime copy. These three tetrads have a mutually similar extremal field-gauge vector structure. They are normalized and a choice of gauge vector has been made. But they are not the same. They could be Lorentz transformed into each other, under non-trivial Lorentz spatial rotations, for instance. We know from manuscript³ that a local Lorentz transformation of a tetrad with an extremal field-gauge vector structure transforms into another tetrad with a similar extremal field-gauge vector structure, even though the skeletons will not be the same, indeed. Therefore, we are considering three local tetrads at the same spacetime point which are not the same for different copies. This is what we mean by three LB1 or LB2 groups under tensor product. Now, from a practical point of view what we also mean by these theorems is that we are able to reconstruct the original local $SU(2)$ gauge transformation by knowing for example, the boosts in the LB1 case, or the spatial rotations in the LB2 case, for the tetrad local transformations at the point under consideration. By knowing the local

Lorentz transformation values for the three copies, and given all the fields, specially the three tetrads at the same point, we can reconstruct the local $SU(2)$ supergauge transformation that gave rise either to three local LB1 transformations or independently to three local LB2 spatial transformations. Because the theorems proved, represent local isomorphisms between either three LB1 groups and supergauge $SU(2)$ or independently three LB2 groups and supergauge $SU(2)$.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We set out to prove that generalized non-Abelian local supergauge transformations are isomorphic to local groups of spacetime tetrad transformations. We thus managed to prove in the non-Abelian $SU(2)$ case that this local group of non-Abelian local gauge transformations in superspace is isomorphic to the local spacetime group of tetrad transformations $(\otimes LB1)^3$. This is not a trivial result. We might argue that we already knew that in the case of local standard gauge transformations in the Standard Model, the local $SU(2)$ was isomorphic to the local group of spacetime tetrad transformations $(\otimes LB1)^3$ in four-dimensional Lorentzian flat or curved spacetimes. The new element is that we managed in this paper to construct tetrad skeletons that are manifestly invariant under generalized non-Abelian local supergauge transformations in superspace. This is the non-trivial element and the contribution in this manuscript. Proving that all the local gauge transformations are isomorphic to local groups of tetrad transformations is equivalent to say that the assumptions made at the outset of the no-go theorems^{4,5,6} are inaccurate as it was analyzed in the introduction. Then, since all the symmetries of the Standard Model are local spacetime symmetries, we argue that microparticles might have associated spacetimes. We argue simultaneously that during an annihilation dynamic process the common four-dimensional spacetime associated to a particle and an antiparticle, like an electron and a positron might get enlarged in both coordinate and field structure to become a superspace. It is this process that we are addressing, because then, multiplets can arise that need to be understood under the light of previous notions. The multiplets in the Standard Model give rise to the existence or represent the features of microparticles. Essentially, put together by common quantum numbers in states. In flat spacetimes. In papers^{1,3} we manage to prove that we can build local tetrads in a curved Lorentz spacetime, that is, in the presence of a gravitational field, such that when

these tetrads are transformed by local gauge transformations, Abelian or non-Abelian, the tetrads rotate locally inside the planes of gauge symmetry. Leaving all the physical local objects invariant. Leaving the metric tensor invariant since we proved that all the local gauge transformations in four-dimensional spacetimes are isomorphic to local Lorentz tetrad transformations. Except for a discrete non-Lorentzian transformation on the local plane one that also leaves the metric tensor invariant. A similar line of reasoning is leading us to hypothesize that during this dynamic annihilation, there could be local gauge transformations transforming local tetrad states into each other, inside these local planes of symmetry. That is, keeping the metric tensor invariant under these tetrad local transformations generated by superspace non-Abelian local supergauge transformations. Supersymmetric local transformations would be responsible for the transformation of the tetrads from non-null into null, which is equivalent to say, by transforming the tetrad skeletons from non-null into null. However, this is material for a future work. Suffice to say that all we have proven in this paper are isomorphisms in flat four-dimensional Lorentz spacetimes. It would be necessary to extend these results into curved four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes, that is, with the presence of gravitational fields and again this is material for another future manuscript. We aim to produce through the tensor products of the isomorphic groups LB1 and LB2 the unification of the Supersymmetric Standard Model and General Relativity on one hand, and on the other hand grand group unification of all the local internal groups of the Supersymmetric Standard Model and all the local spacetime groups of General Relativity. We quote from¹⁹ “Nevertheless, summarizing the results of three years’ work I conclude that under the continual support by Golfand, I had solved the problem formulated by him, that is, I demonstrated the quantum field realization of supersymmetry by a specific example. What stimulated Golfand to formulate the problem ?. It is clear that it was not any specific experimental result such as constant speed of light or the approximate equality of the neutron and proton masses. There were also no questions of overcoming some internal contradictions in field theory as it took place in constructing general relativity or the Weinberg-Salam model. I think that he was inspired by numerous positive results which were obtained by applying one or another symmetry in physics during the 20th century”.

V. APPENDIX I

The object $\sigma^{\alpha\beta}$ is defined as⁷⁻¹⁴ $\sigma^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{i}{4}(\sigma^\alpha \bar{\sigma}^\beta - \sigma^\beta \bar{\sigma}^\alpha)$. The objects σ^α and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha$ arise when building the Weyl representation for left handed and right handed spinors. According to⁷⁻¹¹, they are defined as $\sigma^\alpha = (\mathbf{1}, \sigma^i)$ and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha = (\mathbf{1}, -\sigma^i)$, where σ^i are the Pauli matrices for $i = 1 \cdots 3$. Under the $(\frac{1}{2}, 0)$ and $(0, \frac{1}{2})$ spinor representations of the Lorentz group they transform as,

$$S_{(1/2)}^{-1} \sigma^\alpha S_{(1/2)} = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \sigma^\gamma \quad (27)$$

$$S_{(1/2)}^{-1} \bar{\sigma}^\alpha S_{(1/2)} = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \bar{\sigma}^\gamma . \quad (28)$$

Equations (27-28) mean that under the spinor representation of the Lorentz group, σ^α and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha$ transform the same way as vectors. In (27-28), the matrices $S_{(1/2)}$ are local, as well as Λ^α_γ , see reference¹¹. The $SU(2)$ elements can be considered to belong to the Weyl spinor representation of the Lorentz group. Since the group $SU(2)$ is homomorphic to $SO(3)$, they just represent local space rotations. It is also possible to define the object $\bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{i}{4}(\bar{\sigma}^\alpha \sigma^\beta - \bar{\sigma}^\beta \sigma^\alpha)$, analogously. Then, we have,

$$(\sigma^{\alpha\beta} + \bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \alpha = 0 \text{ and } \beta = i \\ \epsilon^{ijk} \sigma^k & \text{if } \alpha = i \text{ and } \beta = j \end{cases} ,$$

$$(\sigma^{\alpha\beta} - \bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta}) = \begin{cases} -i \sigma^i & \text{if } \alpha = 0 \text{ and } \beta = i \\ 0 & \text{if } \alpha = i \text{ and } \beta = j \end{cases} .$$

We can state for example self and antiself duality properties of these objects⁹ $\sigma^{\alpha\beta}$ and $\bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta}$,

$$\sigma^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2i} \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \sigma_{\gamma\delta} \quad (29)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta} = -\frac{1}{2i} \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \bar{\sigma}_{\gamma\delta} . \quad (30)$$

From reference¹⁴ we also know that,

$$(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a^b (\sigma_{\mu\nu})_c^d = 2\delta_a^d \delta_c^b - \delta_a^b \delta_c^d \quad (31)$$

$$(\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})_{\dot{a}}^{\dot{b}} (\bar{\sigma}_{\mu\nu})_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{d}} = 2\delta_{\dot{a}}^{\dot{d}} \delta_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{b}} - \delta_{\dot{a}}^{\dot{b}} \delta_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{d}} \quad (32)$$

$$(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a^b (\bar{\sigma}_{\mu\nu})_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{d}} = 0 . \quad (33)$$

For $SL(2, C)$ group elements M , the analogous equations to (27-28) are¹⁴,

$$M^{-1} \sigma^\alpha (M^{-1})^\dagger = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \sigma^\gamma \quad (34)$$

$$M^\dagger \bar{\sigma}^\alpha M = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \bar{\sigma}^\gamma . \quad (35)$$

We follow in general the notation in⁹ and since we will not write all these objects properties, we cite fundamentally the references⁷⁻¹⁴.

VI. APPENDIX II

We introduce in this second appendix more objects that we will need in order to construct the tetrads⁷⁻¹⁵ in section II. Either the “skeleton” of the tetrad, or the “gauge vector” fields X^μ and Y^μ . We start with the Hermitian matrices σ_{ab}^μ introduced by Infeld and van der Waerden,

$$\sigma_{ab}^\mu \sigma^{\nu ab} = \eta^{\mu\nu} . \quad (36)$$

In this work on a flat background, $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the Minkowsky metric tensor in four-dimensional spacetime with signature $(-+++)$. Latin indices are the spinor indices taking values 0 and 1, while the primed latin indices refer to the complex conjugate taking values $\dot{0}$ and $\dot{1}$. A detailed discussion is included in reference¹⁵ chapter eight. Therefore we summarize the main relations and expressions involved in our work.

$$\sigma_{ab}^\mu \sigma_{cd}^\nu \eta_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{abcd} . \quad (37)$$

$$\eta_{abcd} = \epsilon_{ac} \epsilon_{bd} . \quad (38)$$

ϵ_{ac} and $\epsilon_{\dot{b}\dot{d}}$ are the skew symmetric Levi-Civita metric spinors, both with components $\epsilon_{00} = \epsilon_{\dot{0}\dot{0}} = 0$, $\epsilon_{01} = \epsilon_{\dot{0}\dot{1}} = -1$, $\epsilon_{11} = \epsilon_{\dot{1}\dot{1}} = 0$ and $\epsilon_{10} = \epsilon_{\dot{1}\dot{0}} = 1$.

$$\theta_a = \epsilon_{ab} \theta^b \quad (39)$$

$$\theta^a = \epsilon^{ab} \theta_b . \quad (40)$$

The metric spinors ϵ^{ab} and $\epsilon^{\dot{a}\dot{b}}$ with components $\epsilon^{00} = \epsilon^{\dot{0}\dot{0}} = 0$, $\epsilon^{01} = \epsilon^{\dot{0}\dot{1}} = 1$, $\epsilon^{11} = \epsilon^{\dot{1}\dot{1}} = 0$ and $\epsilon^{10} = \epsilon^{\dot{1}\dot{0}} = -1$. θ^a are local two-spinors, the index $a = 1, 2$ spanning a complex two dimensional vector space \mathcal{C} at each spacetime point, see reference¹⁵, chapter ten. In the complex conjugate to this vector space $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$ the indices are raised and lowered using the $\epsilon_{\dot{b}\dot{d}}$ metric spinor,

$$\bar{\theta}_{\dot{a}} = \epsilon_{\dot{a}\dot{b}} \bar{\theta}^{\dot{b}} \quad (41)$$

$$\bar{\theta}^{\dot{a}} = \epsilon^{\dot{a}\dot{b}} \bar{\theta}_{\dot{b}} . \quad (42)$$

Since ϵ^{ab} belongs to the tensor product $\mathcal{C} \otimes \mathcal{C}$, it transforms under $SL(2, C)$ as,

$$\epsilon'^{ab} = \epsilon^{cd} S_c^a S_d^b = (\det S) \epsilon^{ab} , \quad (43)$$

where $\det S$ stands for the determinant of the $SL(2, C)$ transformation S_a^b , which means that $\det S = 1$. ϵ^{ab} is a metric spinor, that is why it is used for raising and lowering spinor indices. Likewise for $\epsilon^{\dot{a}\dot{b}}$.

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